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Hierarchy Of Authority And Rules And Regulations As Correlate Of Teachers Job Performance In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated hierarchy of authority and rules and regulations as correlate of teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The design of the study was correlation design. The population of the study was 6,893 teachers in 313 public senior secondary schools while the sample consisted of 550 teachers using simple random sampling technique. The instruments used were Bureaucratic Principles Questionnaire and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire. The instruments were validated by the research supervisors and one other expert in Test and Measurement. The reliability of the instruments yielded index of .87 for Bureaucratic Principles and Teachers' Job Performance was .84 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Out 550 copies of the questionnaire administered, 528 copies were properly filled and retrieved which represented 96% return rate. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation for all the research questions and the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using r-ratio. The findings among others revealed that hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle has a high positive correlation with teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The hypothesis showed that there is a significant correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance. Based on the research finding, bureaucratic principles of hierarchy of authority and rules and regulations have high and positive correlation with teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others newly employed teachers should be given orientation and provided with organogram showing the hierarchy of authority in Public Senior Secondary Schools to enable them respect school authorities.

Keywords: hierarchy of authority, job performance, teachers

INTRODUCTION

Most often, principals are blamed for poor results of students. Parents see the principals of such schools as ineffective and unproductive in the execution of their duties especially when their children perform poorly. Principals direct the activities of teachers who are personnel and sometimes are faced with various administrative challenges in the school setting. Secondary school system is a typical bureaucratic organisation where responsibilities are carried out according to the organisational structures and laid down procedures based on existing rules and regulations. School bureaucratic principle has turned teachers into followers of rules and regulations and not as instructors, mentors and instructional implementers.

Many school administrators or principals have undergone several professional trainings just to acquire worthwhile knowledge, skills and attitude that will help them in performing their assigned roles effectively. As a matter of fact, despite the principal's professional competence and skills to manage the school, the principal has no free hand to run the school as he may wish or take outright decisions. In some cases, rules and regulations, laws and procedures created by the Ministry of Education to

guide the principals' action and role performance have turned out to hinder the success of educational programme.

Weber in Peretomode (2014) identified the following as features of bureaucratic principles: division of labour, hierarchy of authority, rules and regulations, impersonal orientation, free selection of appointed officials, full time paid officials, career orientation and written records/documentation. Also, Weber in Abraham (2003) saw bureaucratisation as an important means of achieving organisational goals and objectives; in order to attain the highest level of efficiency and quality output, bureaucratic principles act as a means to organize and standardize the activities carried out by the principal and teachers in the school. Bureaucratic principles are seen as central control mechanism to shape and reshape teachers' activities to ensure peace, orderliness, accountability, stability and maximum teachers' job performance in the school system.

Muringani (2011) said that bureaucratic principles have really affected principals' leadership styles and practices and also made their administration to be completely impersonal. The principal who is conceived as a leader, a manager and supervisor play a vital role in the administration of secondary schools: he plans, organizes, coordinates the school activities and assigns duties to subordinates for effective management. School as a bureaucratic organisation, must possess the authority, rules and regulations, impersonal orientation, written record /documentation, career orientation. The feature of division of labour and specialisation enable the principal to map out duties and functions according to workers areas of specialisations which helps in achieving school targeted goals. Appropriate division of labour enhances cooperation and coordination, efficiency and effectiveness among workers. For instance, in the school system, teachers are employed to perform teaching and other extracurricular activities that may arise in the school system. Bureaucracy in the school is to be managed by the school administrator so as to give teaching staff the leverage to perform their duties in order to achieve the school objectives within a specific time frame.

Statement of the Problem

The problems of division of labour, hierarchy of authority, rules and regulations, impersonal orientation, career orientation and written documentation have been confronting present day school administrators which perhaps have brought about the poor teachers' job performance in Public Secondary Schools. The classroom setting in Nigeria is generally criticized, among others for being too bureaucratic, too conservative for teachers' management. In developing nations like Nigeria, bureaucratic principles are basically linked with unnecessary red-tapism and inefficiency. This stigma has undermined the functionality of bureaucratic principles in the third world countries. This has equally created doubts in the minds of many whether it is actually suitable for large organizations like the civil service or school as a formal organization. It is noticed in bureaucratic organizations like the school that the introduction of change and innovations or reasoning may not be encouraged because of stringent bureaucratic rules which must be complied with and which hinders the teachers' job performance. It is backdrop that the researcher sought to investigate hierarchy of authority and rules and regulations as correlate of teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study investigated hierarchy of authority and rules and regulations as correlate of teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- 3) find out the extent hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle correlate teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
- 4) identify the extent rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle correlate teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

3. To what extent does hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle correlate teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?
4. To what extent do rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle correlate teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided this study

1. There is no significant correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Hierarchy of Authority and Teachers' Job Performance

School as a bureaucratic organization engages in a communication flow from the top to the bottom, while feedback is from down to the top, the principles of hierarchy of authority delays administrative decision-making process in a large organization like schools. Files and documents have to pass through all the necessary stages, processed and endorsed by the appropriate authorities and officers before the final decision is taken irrespective of the urgent nature of such document. Afangideh (2004) identified that pyramidal hierarchy of authority in organizations distorts and block communication, fosters bureaucratic red-tapism, stifles creativity and innovation, encourages flattery and systematic distortion of the real situation. The above analysis was supported by Okorie (2012), Adesina and Ogunsaju in Ajuzieogu (2008) who pointed out that principals and heads of school no longer exercise independence and freedom which heads of secondary schools enjoyed in the past over such matters as staffing, finance, control of teachers and even the use of school building. The school system has organizational structure, or framework which guides and directs the principals, they receive laws and implement those laws, they communicate to the ministry and disseminate the information to their subordinates. The principals must follow a due process in handling any matter, no matter how urgent the case might be. He cannot act on his own power and any action taken by him constitutes a deviation which leads to sanction which might hinder teachers' job performance.

Every institution requires fund to achieve their goals, money is needed to purchase school equipment, instructional materials, maintenance of already purchased facilities and so on. School principals work hard to generate fund for the success of their schools. Nigeria school system is funded by the three tiers of government. Nwachukwu (2005) complained bitterly about the poor nature of secondary schools as a result of funding. No organization can survive or carry out its function effectively without adequate financial resources at its disposal (Ozgn in Afolabi et al. 2008). Hence the secondary school goals cannot be achieved without addressing the issue of money.

Amadi (2007) lamented that lack of finance, libraries in schools have scanty books, scientific equipment and readers are demoralized as well as indiscipline in schools. In Nigeria, education is not well founded because of inadequate national income, insufficient allocation of funds, lack of planning and accurate statistics, poor leadership style and ignorance of the school principal to utilize grass root method in raising funds. However, all these factors have been a setback in the administrative activities of the school principals. The principal cannot repair or maintain any school equipment or property that needed urgent attention because he has to queue before his time of attention which impedes teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Ajuzieogu (2008) noted that a hierarchical structure tends to be functionally desirable for organisations, which engage in simple routine task but weak for innovative and complex organisation. Okorie (2012) also added that hierarchy of authority stifles creativity, innovation and blockage in communication. The principal and the teachers are implementers of decision made by the upper authority, they hinder them from implementing their creative and innovative ideas because the system bestows its rewards for disciplined compliance with directives from the above.

This principle assists school managers and administrators in managing the institution effectively. The hierarchy of authority shows the chain of command and steps of subordinate/superior relationship in the organization. From the low level to the top level, it is a control and directive mechanism to ensure that competent people perform the right job and at the right time. In terms of decision making, the top management makes the overall decisions that are communicated to the middle level management and to the operative management. The rationale behind the establishment of this principle is to achieve efficiency and effectiveness in the management of both human and material resources in schools. The principle of hierarchy makes it possible for division of organization into different units and sub-units that assist the employees to identify the units, their jobs and responsibilities. These units are arranged

in pyramidal form and the authority and commands describe from the top downwards in a step-by-step manner to the bottom.

For instance how authority follows in Public Senior Secondary Schools.

Fig. 1: Authority Flow from PUBLIC Senior Secondary Schools

Source: Researcher field work, 2022

The diagram shows the super-ordinate/subordinate relationship. It shows that the Schools Management committee is at the apex of the school institution with various line managers. The schools-based management committee communicates to the principal who in turn communicates to his vice principals, the vice principals communicate to the heads of department, the HOD's communicate to teachers and teachers communicate to students, while feedback flows from down to the top, from students to - teachers, HOD - Vice principal — principal — schools management committee for effective decision making. The diagram shows that authority and responsibility must follow from the chain unbroken from the top managers to the bottom. In support of this Afandigah (2004) was of the view that the principals' position in the hierarchy is between the school's board, teachers and other school personnel.

He also postulated that the principals receive directions, from the school board and disseminate these among their staff. Peretomode (2014) opined that positions of offices in school set-up are organized and arranged in form of pyramid. The principal who is at the top pyramid must recognize the line of authority accordingly in order to achieve great success in performing his assigned duties. Afangidah (2014) was of the view that hierarchy of authority allows for a graduation of authority starting with the administrative post and ending with cooperative workers. This principle of hierarchy serves as an instrument through which every part of the organization functions effectively because of channel of communication and clarification of position which are well defined.

Rules and Regulations and Teachers' Job Performance

School as a bureaucratic organisation has formal established laws, policies and procedures which guide every activity in the school system and every member of such system must abide by such laws, rules and regulations. In schools, rules and regulations enable the principals to give directives to the staff and as well receive goal compliance from them. Okorie (2012:16) identified that "one important function of rules and regulation is that they can be applied equally to superiors and subordinates, thereby providing a sense of egalitarianism among the employee". However, the excessive application of rules and regulations in school organisation can lead to conflicts, frustration, over dependence on rules and regulations as well as promoting bureaucratic redtapism, stagnation, inability to adapt to change, excessive delay in decision making because of following procedures and due process. In agreement with the above analysis, Okorie (2012) identified the following disadvantages of rules and regulations as: it leads to redtapism, impairs innovativeness and inability to take responsibility.

Rules and regulation foster impersonal relationship as the principal deals with the students and staff. The principal treat everybody equally without given attention to those who have emotional challenges. Strict adherence to rules and regulation tends to breed resistance to change and

innovation; communication problem, delay in decision making because of conformity to rules and regulation. Peretomode (2014: 32) stated that “there is the inability of bureaucratic principles to respond to change because of its ritualistic attachment to routine procedures”. Strict application of those rules and regulations impairs staff creativity, innovative ideas and ability to responsibility. Hence the authority gives order; the principal must obey and carry it out. Webers conception was that rules are complete guides to action but cannot be substantiated in practice, especially in periods of rapid changes in the society. The principals are just representative of Public Senior Secondary Schools authority because this authority makes polices which shape the operations of schools’ system and its decisions.

Okonkwo in Ajuzieogu (2008) stated that the ministry of education and education services board perform the major jobs, set out rules and guide secondary schools. The principals act as followers of instructions and procedures and not as leaders and managers who can stand and command the subordinates’ immediate compliance. He must seek permission from the higher authority in course of disciplining the staff, students and due process must be followed. Peretomode (2014) described Webers’ model as a machine model since the organization consisting of people is viewed as a machine. The way a machine is built with a particular set of specifications for accomplishing a task is the way Weberian organisation is constructed according to a blue print to achieve a given purpose. The machine model fails to consider difficulties that may be encountered in ranging organisation made of different individuals because of strict adherence to rules and regulation. Principals, Staff and students have little or no opportunities to put in their creative and innovative ideas. The world is now a global village, things have changed from what they used to be, the old method of teaching and learning have changed and some have become obsolete. Before now chalk boards were used, but in this present era, laptop, projector, white marker board are new innovation in education system.

METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was correlation design. The population of the study was 6,893 teachers in 313 public senior secondary schools while the sample consisted of 550 teachers using simple random sampling technique. The instruments used were Bureaucratic Principles Questionnaire and Teachers’ Job Performance Questionnaire. The instruments were validated by the research supervisors and one other expert in Test and Measurement. The reliability of the instruments yielded index of .87 for Bureaucratic Principles and Teachers’ Job Performance was .84 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Out 550 copies of the questionnaire administered, 528 copies were properly filled and retrieved which represented 96% return rate. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation for all the research questions and the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using r-ratio.

RESULTS

Research question 1: *To what extent does hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle correlate teachers’ job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers’ job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	N	Df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Hierarchy of authority (X)	8531	2451	528	526	2562	0.79	High Positive Correlation
Teachers’ job performance (Y)	21220	3349					

Source: Researcher’s Field Result, 2024

Result from Table 1 showed the correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance. The table reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.79. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance. This implies that emphasis on hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle will lead to corresponding improvement in teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Research question 2: *To what extent do rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle correlate teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Rules and regulations (X)	21411	2123	528	526	2241	0.86	High Positive Correlation
Teachers' job performance (Y)	21220	3349					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

Result from Table 2 showed the correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers job performance. The table reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.86. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance. This implies that adherence to rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle will lead to corresponding improvement in teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Transformed z-ratio on the Correlation Between Hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Hierarchy of authority (X)	8531	2451	528	526	2562	0.79	28.01	1.96	Sig. Rejected H_0
Teachers' job performance (Y)	21220	3349							

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

Result from Table 3 revealed that a high positive correlation exists between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the correlation, a transformed z-value was computed and an index of 28.01 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 526, indicating that there is a significant positive correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance (calculated $z = 28.01 < \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 526$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance is rejected. This implies that the correlation is positive and strong, and adherence on hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle tends to be accompanied by improvement in teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Transformed z-ratio on the Correlation Between Rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Rules and regulations (X)	21411	2123	528	526	2241	0.86	35.32	1.96	Sig. Rejected H_0
Teachers' job performance (Y)	21220	3349							

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

Result from Table 4 revealed that a high positive correlation exists between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the correlation, a transformed z-value was computed and an index of 35.32 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 526, indicating that there is a significant positive correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance (calculated $z = 35.32 < \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 526$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance is rejected. This implies that the correlation is positive and strong, and any increase in use of rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle tends to be accompanied by improvement in teachers' job performance in public Senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hierarchy of Authority and Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools

The study found that hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle has a high positive correlation with teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study is in agreement with Okorie (2010) who believed that school like other formal organisation has hierarchical arrangement. In school structure, the authority is generally concentrated at the high level management and the information always flows from top to the bottom. The principal who is seen as the executive receives order from the central authority, communicate to his vice principal who communicates to the head of department, then HOD communicates to the teachers and students.

This principle assists school managers and administrators in managing the institution effectively. The hierarchy of authority shows the chain of command and steps of subordinate/superior correlation in the organization. From the low level to the top level, it is a control and directive mechanism to ensure that competent people perform the right job and at the right time. In terms of decision making, the top management makes the overall decisions that are communicated to the middle level management and to the operative management. The rationale behind the establishment of this principle is to achieve efficiency and effectiveness in the management of both human and material resources in schools. The principle of hierarchy makes it possible for division of organization into different units and sub-units that assist the employees to identify the units, their jobs and responsibilities.

Ibira (2011) opined that authority can be exercised effectively in an organisation when positions are hierarchically arranged. So, employees know whom to report to and who reports to them. The hierarchy of authority enables every member of the organisation to understand his or her position, his responsibilities, who he is accountable to, and also help in eliminating conflicts and confusion. In the administration of school authority rests on the position and not actually on the person occupying such position.

Afangideh (2004) believed that the pyramidal hierarchy of authority in organizations improves communication, fosters bureaucratic respect, creativity and innovation and it encourages systematic skills of the real situation. Files and documents have to pass through all the necessary stages, processed and endorsed by the appropriate authorities and officers before the final decision is taken. Udo (2008) said that Principals or heads of school's exercise independence and freedom which heads

of secondary schools enjoys on matters as: staffing clerical officers, finance, control of teachers and use of school building.

Furthermore, the school system has organizational structure, or framework which guides and direct the principals, they receive laws and implement those laws, they communicate to the ministry and disseminate the information to their subordinates. The principals follow a due process in handling any matter, no matter how urgent the case might be. He cannot act on his own power and any action taken by him constitutes a deviation which leads to sanction which might hinder teachers' job performance. The hierarchy of authority shows the chain of command and steps of subordinate/superior correlation in the organization. From the low level to the top level, it is a control and directive mechanism to ensure that competent people perform the right job and at the right time. In terms of decision making, the top management makes the overall decisions that are communicated to the middle level management and to the operative management. The rationale behind the establishment of this principle is to achieve efficiency and effectiveness in the management of both human and material resources in schools.

Peretomode (2014) opined that positions of offices in school set-up are organized and arranged in form of pyramid. The principal who is at the top pyramid must recognize the line of authority accordingly in order to achieve great success in performing his assigned duties. Afangidah (2014) was of the view that hierarchy of authority allows for a graduation of authority starting with the administrative post and ending with cooperative workers. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance is rejected. This implies that the correlation is positive and strong, and any improvement in hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle tends to be accompanied by improvement in teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Rules and Regulations and Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools

The study found that rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle has a high positive correlation with teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study is in agreement with Afangideh (2004) that in school system, rules and regulations guide the activities of every member, no matter how well an organization is structured, without law, procedures, rules and regulations such an organisation will never actualize its goals. Rules and regulation maintain peace and order in the school's system. The rules guide the school principals' decision and also direct teachers, students and non-academic personnel on the dos and don'ts.

The teachers have to adapt and be conversant with the new development, no parent would like to take their children to a school where things are not done in a modernised way. It is expected that school principals who want to achieve equilibrium in his administration should be innovative and creative in the development and management of school resources and also endeavor to change along by providing the new skills, new infrastructure and instructional materials in the school to make teaching and learning less difficult.

According to Okorie (2012), one important function of rules and regulation is that they can be applied equally to superiors and subordinates, thereby providing a sense of egalitarianism among the employee". However, the excessive application of rules and regulations in school organisation can lead to conflicts, frustration, over dependence on rules and regulations as well as promoting bureaucratic redtapism, stagnation, inability to adapt to change, excessive delay in decision making because of following procedures and due process. The principal treat everybody equally, without given attention to those who have emotional challenges. Strict adherence to rules and regulation tends to breed resistance to change and innovation; communication problem, delay in decision making because of conformity to rules and regulation.

Peretomode (2014) put it this way that rules and regulations spell out the rights and duties inherent in each position and help in stability of employees' action. Ehiodo (2006) stated that rules and regulations are not made for any particular individual rather for the post and offices that are created in that organization. Rules ensure uniformity and regulate the actions of employers and employees, creating cordial correlation among institutional members. In Webers conception, he believed that bureaucracies should be governed by rules and regulations, which every member must obey in order for the organisation to achieve its set goals.

Okonkwo in Ajuzieogu (2008) stated that the ministry of education and education services board perform the major jobs, set out rules and guide secondary schools. The principals act as followers of instructions and procedures and not as leaders and managers who can stand and command the subordinates' immediate compliance. Peretomode (2014) stated that "there is the inability of bureaucracy to respond to change because of its ritualistic attachment to routine procedures" strict application of those rules and regulations impairs staff creativity, innovative ideas and ability to responsibility.

This deduction agrees with the findings of the present study. This implies that a principal must seek permission from the higher authority in the course of disciplining the staff and students, meaning that the due process must be followed. This act, impedes effectiveness in school administration, as well as frustrates the efforts of principals in fostering a healthy and disciplined environment for teaching and learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance is rejected. This implies that the correlation is positive and strong, and any improvement in rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle tends to be accompanied by improvement in teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study are summarized as shown below:

3. Table 1 found that hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle has a high positive correlation with teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
4. Table 2 found that rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle has a high positive correlation with teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary schools in Rivers State.
5. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance is rejected. This implies that the correlation is positive and strong, and any improvement in hierarchy of authority as bureaucratic principle tends to be accompanied by improvement in teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
6. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant correlation between rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle and teachers' job performance is rejected. This implies that the correlation is positive and strong, and any improvement in rules and regulations as bureaucratic principle tends to be accompanied by improvement in teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research finding, bureaucratic principles of hierarchy of authority and rules and regulations have high and positive correlation with teachers' job performance. The study has also established that components of bureaucratic principles such as hierarchy of authority and rules and regulations hypothetically significantly correlate teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Newly employed teachers should be given orientation and provided with organogram showing the hierarchy of authority in Public Senior Secondary Schools to enable them respect school authorities.
2. School rules and regulations should be in a document format to all teachers for their perusal, keeps and emphasized during orientations exercises.

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